
THE EFFECT OF WRITING-TO-LEARN INSTRUCTIONAL STRATEGY ON STUDENTS' PERFORMANCE IN MATHEMATICS: A CASE STUDY OF SOME SELECTED SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN MAKURDI LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, BENUE STATE

¹MBAM, Gilbert Ofoke, ²OLUSANYA, Abdulrasaq Oluwole

¹Statistics Department, Nigerian Army College of Environmental Science and Technology, Makurdi, Benue State. gilbertofoke01@gmail.com

²Sikiru Adetona College of Education, Science and Technology, Omu Ajose, Ogun State. oluolusanya@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

This study examined the effect of writing-to-learn instructional strategy on students' performance in Mathematics. It equally determined the moderating effect of gender on students' performance in Mathematics. Five hypotheses guided the study. Pretest-posttest-control group quasi-experimental design with a 2x2 factorial arrangement was adopted for the study. One hundred and twenty four (124) students of senior secondary two (SS2) from the two selected public senior secondary schools in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue state constituted the sample. Mathematics Achievement Test in trigonometry (MAT, $r = 0.760$) was used for data collection. Data collected was analyzed through inferential statistics of analysis of covariance (ANCOVA). The finding indicated that writing-to-learn instructional strategy significantly improved students' performance in mathematics and the strategy (writing to learn) is not sensitive to gender since there is no interaction effect of gender and the strategy on students' performance in Mathematics. The result of the study discovered also that gender (male and female) is not a strong factor affecting the learning of mathematics in senior secondary schools. The finding also revealed that writing-to-learn strategy enhanced students' knowledge retention of mathematics/mathematics concepts, and there is no interaction effect of gender and strategy on students' retention in Mathematics. Consequently, the finding suggest that teachers should adopt writing-to-learn strategy in the teaching and learning of mathematics in senior secondary schools. Therefore, one of the recommendations is that writing-to-learn strategy should be included in the teacher education programme as one of the methods in the mathematics method, to enable a would be mathematics teacher to master the nitty-gritty associated with the strategy.

Keywords: Performance, retention, gender, writing-to-learn, conventional

INTRODUCTION

Mathematics is one of the most central components of human thought, considered to be the oldest field of study in the history of mankind (Mohamed, 2010). Mathematics sharpens the human mind, develops their logical thinking, enhance reasoning ability and spatial power for effective management of our environment. According to Akinoso (2015), mathematics is useful in keeping of records such as addition, subtraction, division and multiplication of numbers, money, length, mass and time. It also plays an important role in vocations such as carpentry, tailoring, and plumbing which need the basic knowledge of geometry involving measurement, angle, symmetry and plane shapes. Mathematics is also useful in other subjects such as science, geography, accounting and economics in calculation of population density, gradient, just to mention but few. Enikanolaye et al (2017) submitted that the usefulness of mathematics carries with it the assumption that the knowledge of mathematics is substantive for all members of the society. This means that technological and economic growth of any society depend on the application of mathematical knowledge by the members of the society.

Despite the importance of mathematics, most students today experience difficulty in learning Mathematics, which has led to their feeling that Mathematics is not an interesting subject to learn. This, among other factors has equally resulted to poor performance of students in Mathematics.

Scholars (Iji & Uka, 2012; Achuonye, 2015; Forgye et al, 2017; Nyakomba 2017) have attributed this poor performance to some other factors such as teachers' attitude and belief, poor teaching methodology, etc. However, when students' performance in Mathematics is poor, teacher's pedagogy would be the first to be blamed. The importance of mathematics to both human and societal development demands that effective teaching and learning strategies are needed to enhance students' learning and academic performance in the subject. Mathematics learning is largely shaped by the teacher and the tasks proposed, as well as the strategies used to convey them (Vale & Barbosa, 2023). This means that the teacher through thoughtful choice of strategies and tasks, should contribute to students' development of mathematical understanding, by creating opportunities for them to be challenged and engage in higher order thinking. Students learn in different ways base on their peculiarity. Therefore, there is need to adopt a teaching strategy that would bring about interaction between intellectual, social and physical environment as three strands in the context of active learning, for lasting learning outcome. Active learning has its roots in the socio-constructivist theory of learning, and it is a classroom practice that engages students in activities such as talking, listening, writing and other activities that bring about learning (Vale & Barbose, 2023).

Writing is an integral part of learning. Writing-to-learn (WTL) is the act of making a subject or topic clear to oneself by actively reasoning through it in writing. It is a pedagogical approach that uses writing to facilitate learning (Fry & Villagomez, 2012). Writing-to-learn according to Pugalee (2014) is broadly seen as a type of writing that explains mathematical concept, expresses mathematical ideas and problem solving including but not limited to responses and drawings. Writing-to-learn is grounded in the constructivist belief that learning is an active process whereby students construct their own meaning about the content being studied rather than merely being passive recipients of information imparted by teachers (Teuscher *et al*, 2015).

Writing-to-learn teaching strategy encourages students to think on paper thereby making them to construct their own knowledge based on their cognitive development (cognitive constructivism).

Three kinds of writing activities reflect three aspects of learning mathematics. These writing activities are: content writing, process writing and affective writing. Content writing deals with the understanding of mathematical concepts and relations, process writing is concerned with algorithm and problem solving while affective writing focuses on students' feelings and attitudes (Urguhart, 2009).

Procedure for using Writing-to-Learn teaching strategy

There are many ways a teacher could inculcate writing activities in mathematics class based on what the teacher wants to achieve. For this study, students will be engaged with content writing and process writing in Mathematics classroom.

Content writing

The teacher after teaching the students conventionally, presents question or prompt to students concerning their personal understanding of a mathematical concept being studied and task them to explain in writing their understanding about the concept, with examples.

Example;

Learning task:

The teacher provides a concept in trigonometry.

Writing-to-Learn (content writing):

The teacher allows the students to individually explain in writing, what they understand about the concept, with examples and relations to daily activities.

The teacher monitors the activities for some minutes (3min), collects the students' work at random, reads and makes corrections generally in the class for better understanding of the mathematical concept.

Process writing

The teacher provides a solvable problem on trigonometry.

Writing-to-Learn (process writing):

The teacher gives the students time to explain in writing, the step-by-step (algorithm) or the procedure he or she would use to solve the problem.

The teacher monitors and guides the students' activities for some minutes (5min) collects their work at random for correction and to guide the students more in the general class.

The more learners engage with and process course related materials in writing, the more information/knowledge they may potentially retain and eventually internalize (Chmarkh, 2020).

The main strive for education is for meaningful learning to take place. On this note, the retention ability of students cannot be left out. This is because the essence of teaching and learning should include the ability of students to remember what they have been taught over time. In dated years, studies on instructional strategies and retention have allured many researchers (Guwan & Gwandum, 2017; Enikanolaye, 2021).

Gender in a social context is an attribute which shows the difference between male and female. Several directions of views have been guided by research on the influence of gender on students' performance in Mathematics. Adeniyi (2012) in his study on the influence of personalized system of instruction on students' academic performance in mathematics based on gender concluded that students' gender has no influence on their performance. Akanmu (2013) also in his study on the influence of gender on senior school students' performance in mathematics discovered that there is no significant difference in the performance of male and female students when taught using guided discovery method. Jacob and Linus (2017), in contrary submitted that there is a significant difference between the performance of male and female students in geography when taught using Mastery Learning Strategy (MLS). Gender difference has been a reality in education particularly in Sub-Saharan Africa according to Schaumburg (2001). However, there is no uniformity in the agreement of scholars on the issue of gender influence on students' academic achievements.

Problem Statement

Poor performance of students in Mathematics has become a thing of concern to mathematics educators, parents', students, scientists, technician education administrators and government. Since Mathematics is considered a prerequisite subject for admission into higher institution of learning in Nigeria, it is pertinent for students in secondary school to perform well in Mathematics. Teachers' predominant use of conventional method of teaching to teach mathematics and its resultant effect of poor performance of students in external examinations such as West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE) and National Examination Council (NECO) is a problem. It should be the duty of Mathematics educators, government and other stakeholders to find effective teaching strategies that would lead to improvement of students' performance in Mathematics. This, points to the significance of this study, to investigate the impact of active learning strategy such as writing-to-learn instructional strategy on students' performance in Mathematics.

Objective of the Study

The main purpose of the study is to determine the effect of writing-to-learn teaching strategy on students' achievement in mathematics. Specifically, the study will investigate if:

1. There is no significant main effect of writing-to-learn instructional strategy on students' performance in mathematics
2. There is no significant main effect of gender (male and female) on students' performance in mathematics.
3. If there is no interaction effect of writing-to-learn and gender on students' performance in mathematics.
4. If there is no significant main effect of writing-to-learn instructional strategy on students' retention of Mathematics knowledge/concepts.
5. If there is no effect of gender on students' retention of mathematics knowledge/concept.

Research Questions

The following research questions are raised for this study:

1. What is the difference in the performance of students taught Mathematics using writing-to-learn instructional strategy and those taught using conventional method?

2. Does the performance of male and female students differ when taught Mathematics using WTL teaching strategy?
3. Is there any interaction effect of treatment (WTL) and gender on students' performance in mathematics?
4. Is there any difference in the retention of mathematics knowledge/concepts between the students exposed to Writing-to-Learn instructional strategy and those exposed to conventional method?
5. Does gender have any effect on students' mathematics retention when taught using writing to learn strategy?

Statement of the Hypotheses

H₀1: There is no significant main effect of treatment (writing-to-learn strategy) on students' performance in Mathematics.

H₀2: There is no significant main effect of gender (male and Female) on students' performance in mathematics.

H₀3: There is no significant interaction effect of treatment (writing-to-learn) and gender on students' performance in Mathematics.

H₀4: There is no significant main effect of treatment (writing-to-learn) on students' retention in Mathematics.

H₀5: There is no significant main effect of gender on students' retention in Mathematics

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical Review

The theoretical base relevant to this study is constructivism theory of learning. Constructivism according to Elliot et al (2000) is an approach to learning which holds that learners actively construct their knowledge and that reality is determined by the learner. Arends (1998) elaborated that constructivism believes in personal construction of meaning through experience, and that meaning is influenced by interacting with the environment based on prior knowledge and new events. This simply means that acquisition of knowledge is based on active engagement of the learner and interaction of the learner with his environment.

The principles of constructivism according to McLeod (2019) are as follows:

- a. Knowledge is neither innate nor passively acquired, rather it is constructed.
- b. Learning takes place through active process.
- c. Knowledge is socially constructed and is personal. This means that subjective interpretation of things by individual differs.
- d. Learning exists in the mind and not outside the mind. This means that learning does not have to match any real world reality.

Constructivism learning theory is divided into three broad categories. These are: cognitive constructivism, social constructivism and radical constructivism (McLeod, 2019). In the classroom setting, Constructivism approach to teaching demands varieties of learner-centred teaching methods and techniques, in which the teacher's role is that of a facilitator or a guide. Oliver (2000) stressed that the teacher should understand the learners' pre-existing conceptions, and guides the activities to address them and then build on them. In line with

this, Tam (2000) listed some basic characteristics of constructivist learning classroom as follows:

- a. Knowledge should be a shared responsibility between teacher and the learner. This means that the teacher should not take monopoly of the knowledge to indoctrinate the learners.
- b. Authority is to be shared between the teacher and the learners. This implies that the teacher should respect the personality of the learners while in classroom.
- c. Teacher's role should be that of a facilitator or a guide. This means that the teacher should introduce meaningful interactive activities that will bring about learning and guide the learners while engaging them with the activities.
- d. Learners are to be grouped heterogeneously in small numbers. This implies that the teacher should group learners for the purpose of interaction among themselves, and the group should consist of both academically weak and strong learners.

The diagram below according to Nugroho and Wulandari (2017) is the Constructivist learning model

Figure 1: Constructivism learning paradigm model
Source: Nugroho and Wulandari, 2017

Figure 1 above is characterized by three basic components. These components are: learning environment, learning participation and learning responsibility. This implies that if meaningful learning is to take place, the learning environment should be considered to be a constructivist environment which should be activity driven environment, there must be an active participation of learners and the responsibility should be shared between the learners and the teacher. These, lead to knowledge construction and development in learners.

Writing-to-Learn teaching strategy is an active learning strategy which can be associated with constructivism. Writing-to-Learn takes the form of contemplation (active thinking) and developing the thought in writing. Through contemplation and developing the thought into writing (thinking on paper), students' cognition and meta-cognition are being facilitated and developed for knowledge construction. This active thinking brings about cognitive constructivism, which enables students to construct their knowledge based on their level of cognitive development, hence, the relevance of this theory to the study.

Conceptual Review

Writing-to-learn teaching strategy is a participatory technique. It is an active learning strategy. Active learning techniques are instructional activities involving students in doing

things and thinking about what they are doing (Yusuk, 2020). In writing-to-learn strategy, students are being engaged in writing activities. Therefore, active learning could be seen as a classroom situation in which the teacher and instructional activities explicitly afford the students an opportunity to learn through active participation.

Research has proven the effectiveness of writing-to-learn strategy on students' academic achievement and retention (Seo, 2015; Deveci, 2018; Umoren et al, 2024). However, research has shown that the performance of student in mathematics over the years has been in abysmal state (Utibe & Agwagah, 2015; Gogo & Nduka, 2017). Research has also proven that mathematics teachers stick more to teacher-centred (traditional) method which is less effective than the modern teaching method which is activity based (Kumah & Wonu, 2022). This study investigated the impact of Writing-to-Learn instructional strategy on senior secondary school students' performance in mathematics, using some selected secondary schools in Makurdi Local Government Area, Benue state. The conceptual framework for this study is postulating that there are factors such as teachers' teaching strategies as external factors and personal quality such as gender as an internal factor upon which students' performance in mathematics and retention could be predicted. This implies that teachers' teaching methods might not be the only determinants of students' performance and retention in mathematics, personal quality of being male or female, could be other correlate.

These effects between the performance and retention, and explanatory variables used in this study are shown in the diagram below.

Figure 2: Conceptual map of the variables

Figure 2 above shows Writing-to-Learn (WTL) teaching strategy and conventional method as independent variables, academic achievement and retention as dependent variables while gender (male and female) is taken as a moderator variable

Nature of Mathematics, and Teaching and Learning of Mathematics

Mathematics is a unique subject that permeates every facet of human endeavour. The beauty of Mathematics and its importance to human life have led to the approval of March 14 (pi day) as International Day of Mathematics (International Mathematics Union, 2019). According to Oloda *et al* (2024), Mathematics is more than Arithmetic, the science of numbers and computation, more than geometry, the study of shapes, size and space, greater than trigonometry, the study of the relationship between triangles and their angles, more than statistics, the science of collection, presentation analysis and interpretation of data. If Mathematics is more than all these branches, what then is mathematics and its' nature? The nature of mathematics could be deduced from its characteristics as embedded in the various definitions given by scholars.

Yara and Otieno (2010) defined Mathematics as the creation of human mind concerned primarily with ideas, processes and reasoning, when put in practice brings technology. This definition places Mathematics as being abstract in nature since its operation is based on the world of ideas and reasoning. Ugwu (2011) defined mathematics as the study of all structures, whose forms can be expressed in symbols. Ugwu added that mathematics is the grammar of all symbolic system. This definition describes mathematics as being structural and symbolic in nature. Mathematics is also defined as a way of thinking, and organizing of logical proof (Agah, 2020). He (Agah) also added that Mathematics is concerned with answers to questions and problems, with language that uses a carefully defined terms and precision to communicate. This definition presents the nature of mathematics as being logical, precise and problem solving oriented.

The nature of Mathematics can now be seen from the definitions as being abstract, symbolic, precise, structural and logical sequence. Therefore, mathematics teachers should understand these natures of Mathematics for effective teaching of the subject using active learning techniques. Mathematics class should be made interesting by using active and interactive-based strategy, which is Student-Centred and not Teacher-Centred. Teacher-Centred strategy has been criticized by researchers (Achuonye, 2015; Muema et al 2018) for not catering for all students especially those with weak understanding of mathematical concepts. Mathematics teaching according to Aduwa (2021) is the intellectual ability of the mathematics teacher to apply the appropriate teaching techniques or methods in disseminating mathematics contents. These techniques must include activities that would encourage the students towards mathematical reasoning based on their level of cognitive development .hence Writing-to-Learn strategy (WTL). Researchers (Ogbeba, 2010; Bature et al, 2016; Oloda et al, 2024) have established that teacher-centred (conventional) method is the predominant teaching method used by mathematics teachers to teach mathematics in Nigerian secondary schools, hence the need for this study.

Writing-to-learn instructional strategy and academic performance

Abiodun et al (2022) reiterated that many students at secondary school level consider mathematics as abstract and also see it as a subject that is difficult to understand. Writing-to-Learn (WTL) otherwise known as active writing in mathematics class is an Activity-Based and student-centred method of teaching which involves students in creative mathematical writing that enhances their knowledge and understanding of mathematical concepts,

algorithm and problem solving Writing itself is the ability to compose a text effectively for different purposes. Seo (2015) defines writing as an organized collection of symbols that conveys meaning.

Writing brings about retrieval effect and helps to strengthen students' memories of the material they are exposed to learn. Writing about content material facilitates learning by consolidating information in long term memory (Terada 2021). Writing-to-learn according to Kayaalp et al. (2020) does not refer to the students' customary, less active and simple note-taking activity for particular information which the teacher attempt to convey or that is written in textbook. It is a non-traditional and alternative type of writing such as expository or explanatory type of writing or other writing activities in mathematics class that enables students to develop critical thinking skills about what they are learning. This implies that Writing-to-Learn in Mathematics as an instructional strategy is not the same thing as writing a note that has been developed by the teacher or copying what is written in the textbook, rather, it is the type of creative writing that makes students to have an in-depth and retrospective thought about what they have learned, and compose it in form of a text to communicate their thinking and understanding of the concept they have learnt or the algorithm of what they have learnt.

Types of mathematical writing with their purposes according to Kaur and Prendergast (2021) are:

- 1 Exploratory writing (to personally make sense of a problem, situation or one's own ideas)
- 2 Explanatory/Informative writing (to describe, to explain)
- 3 Argumentative writing (to construct or critic an argument)
- 4 Mathematically creative (to document original ideas, problems and/or solutions, to convey fluency and flexibility in thinking, to elaborate on ideas).

Studies have been carried out on Writing-to-learn strategy and its effect on students' academic achievement and retention. Kayaalp et al (2022) investigated the effect of Writing-to-Learn activities on students' academic achievement and self-regulated skill in writing. Quasi-experimental design was adopted which involved sixty-four (64) 8th grade students in Turkey as sample. Tools for data collection were academic achievement test and self-regulated scale for writing and t-test statistics was used to analyze the data. The results revealed that the academic achievement and self-regulated skills of the students in the experimental group were found higher than their counterpart in the control group. The findings also maintained that the experimental group showed knowledge retention over time than the control group.

Joedeve and Mejare (2023) investigated the effects of journal writing on grade 10 students' performance and attitudes towards Mathematics. Quasi-experimental research design was adopted for the study and grade 10 intact classes formed the sample of the study. Mathematics Performance Test (MPT) and Fennema-Sherman mathematics attitude scale were used as instruments for data collection. The result indicated that there is a significant difference on students' academic performance and attitudes in Mathematics in favour of experimental group.

In the same vein, Pantimo et al (2015) examined the effect of Writing-to-Learn strategy on students' achievement in mathematics. Quasi-experimental design was used with a sample of sixty (60) students from three intact classes of college freshman students, university of Iloilo city Philippine. The study had two experimental groups (G1 and G2). G1 was exposed to traditional instruction with individual creative writing (Writing-to-Learn) G2 was exposed to

traditional instruction with group creative writing and control group was exposed to traditional instruction without any writing activity. Mathematics achievement test (MAT) was used as data collection instrument and the analysis of the data revealed that there was no significant difference in the students' achievements. However, the paired sample t-tests showed a significant difference in the students' achievement test score before and after the treatment 1 and 2 and conventional set up.

Again, Incirci and Paemaksiz (2016) investigated the effects of Writing-to-Learn strategy on academic achievement and attitude in English of level 11th grade students in black sea region of Turkey. Mixed method research was used with a sample of eighty-four (84) students. Simple past tense achievement test (SPTAT) was used for data collection. The data was analyzed using Kruskal-Wallis and Mann-Whitney U analysis and it was discovered that there is a statistical difference in the academic achievement of the students in favour of the experimental group.

Umorennet,al (2024) also carried out a study on writing to learn, gender and effects on mathematics achievement of secondary school students in Akwa Ibom state, Nigeria. Quasi-experimental design was employed for the study and mathematics achievement test (MAT) was use for data collection. The analysis of data was done using analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) and the result indicated that there was a significant difference in the achievement of experimental and control groups in favour of the experimental group. The findings equally showed that there was no significant interaction effect of gender and treatment (WTL) on students' achievement in mathematics when taught using writing to learn strategy.

Gender Difference and Academic Performance

Scholars (Aransi, 2018; Sunday & Honmane, 2023; Orbhabor, 2019) have identified some factors responsible for students' poor performance and retention in mathematics. These factors include students' and teachers' attitude, teachers' qualification, teaching methods, school type and government policies, school location, family types and gender difference. However, gender and students' academic performance is still controversial and hence inconclusive. Filgona and Sababa (2017) opined that gender is one of the explanatory variables that needs to be factored in when students' academic achievement in any subject is to be assessed.

Ajai and Imoko (2015) investigated the influence of gender in Mathematics achievement and retention: a case of Problem-Based Learning (PBL) method using SS1 students. Instrument for the data collection was Algebra Achievement Test (AAT). The hypotheses were tested using t-test statistics and the result maintained that male and female students taught algebra using PBL did not significantly differ in achievement and retention in algebra. Again, Anokye-Poku and Ampadu (2020), conducted a research on gender differences in attitude and achievement in Mathematics among Ghanaian Junior High School students. Questionnaire and students' test scores were used for data collection. The findings established that there is a significant difference in the attitude and achievement of male and female students in mathematics, in favour of the male students.

Oribhabor (2019) also examined the influence of gender on academic achievement in Mathematics among Senior Secondary School students in Bayelsa. Survey research design was adopted for the study with a sample of one thousand seven hundred and fifty four (1,754) students. Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions while t-test statistics was used to test the hypotheses. The findings maintained that there is a significant difference in the mathematics achievement of male and female students in favour of the male students.

Not only this Fehintola and Yahya (2019) investigated the effect of gender on Economics students' performance and retention on secondary schools in Oyo, Nigeria using Economics Performance Test (EPT) as an instrument for data collection. The study was a quasi-experimental study involving seventy-seven (77) students in Oyo West Local Government Area. The data collected was analyzed using t-test statistics and the results revealed that gender has no significant influence on secondary school students' performance and retention in Economics. In the same vein, Obidile and Uzoekwe (2018), examined the influence of gender on Accounting students' achievement and retention in secondary school in Anambra state, Nigeria using Accounting Achievement Test (AAT) as an instrument for data collection. The study was a quasi-experimental study and the data collected was analyzed using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). The findings maintained that there is no significant difference in the mean score of male and female students taught Accounting using discussion method of teaching and again, male and female students taught accounting using discussion method had high retention score.

Interaction effect of gender and treatment on students' academic performance has not been left out by scholars. Anari et, al. (2023) investigated the interaction effect of gender and treatment on academic achievement and retention in Chemistry in Calabar educational zone, Cross River state. One hundred and twenty two (122) senior secondary one (SS1) made up the sample of the study and chemistry bonding achievement test (CBAT) was used for data collection. Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was used for data analysis. The result revealed that there was no significant interaction effect of gender and treatment on students' performance. However, the finding equally showed that there was a significant interaction effect of gender and treatment on students' retention in chemistry.

Summary of the Literature Review and Identification of Research Gap

The analysis of the empirical studies reviewed has shown that, researchers have carried out studies on WTL instructional strategy to determine the effects on students' academic achievement and retention. On average, there is a general agreement that WTL instructional strategy has positive effect on students' academic performance based on the work of Inncirci (2016), Keyaalp et al (2022) and Umoren et, al (2024). Also findings on empirical studies of, gender difference and academics performance remains inconclusive.

However, empirical studies cited on WTL are outside Benue state and Makurdi Local Government Area in particular. This implies that attention has not been paid to this particular teaching strategy in Makurdi Local Government Area, Benue state, Nigeria. This is a gap and has necessitated this study.

METHODS

Research Design

The research design adopted for this study was a pretest-posttest control group quasi-experimental design, involving 2x2 factorial matrix. One hundred and twenty six (126) senior secondary two (SS 2) students from the two purposively selected senior secondary schools in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue state participated in the study. The schools were selected based on the criteria that they are state co-education secondary schools with ample population of both sexes to accommodate the introduction of gender as a covariate. Again the willingness of school authorities and subject teachers to allow the implementation of the experiment was also considered in selecting the schools. The distance between the two secondary schools was also taken into consideration to prevent interaction among the students of the selected schools.

Mathematics Achievement test (MAT) on trigonometry was the instrument used for data collection. The MAT is a researcher-developed instrument containing two sections. Section A contains information about students' which includes their gender, while section B contains 40 multiple-choice items which the students answered by choosing from the options provided. The 40 item instrument was obtained from the initial 120-item test, after item analysis. The validities (face and contents) of the instrument were obtained through the critics of experts. The suggestions of the experts were used to fine-tune the instrument. The instrument was administered twice at interval of two weeks on forty (40) senior secondary two (SS 2) students from school that share similar attribute but did not participate in the study, to determine the reliability. The scores obtained were analysed using Kuder Richardson formula (KR) 21 which yielded a coefficient of 0.760. The experimental study lasted for six (6) weeks. Week one (1) was designated to training of two teachers and the students in the experimental group on the implementation of writing-to-learn instructional strategy. After the training, Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) was administered to the students in both experimental and control groups as the pre-test. In week two, students in the experimental group were exposed to trigonometry as a topic through writing-to-learn instructional strategy.

The teacher started each class with conventional approach by explaining the concepts and solving problems related to the selected topic. Thereafter, students were given a writing prompts (content writing) and process prompts (process writing) on the topic they have been taught. Each student was given 15 minutes to individually write and explain their understanding of a given concept they have been taught, solve a given problem by explaining in writing, the processes (algorithm) taken to solve the problem while the teacher monitors the activities. The teacher gave classwork and assignment after each class to obtain feedback from the students. Remedial classes were also organized for students that did not perform well in the exercises. However, students in the control group were taught using conventional method which did not involve the use of writing-to-learn strategy. At the five weeks, reshuffled version of MAT was administered to the students in the two groups as the post-test. Again, after two weeks of the post-test, the reshuffled version of the post-test was administered to the students of the two groups as retention test. The data collected were analysed through inferential statistics of analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) using IBM SPSS Statistics 23.

Findings

The findings from the data analysis are presented below:

H₀1: There is no significant main effect of treatment (writing-to-learn instructional strategy) on students' performance in mathematics.

Table 1: Main and Interaction effects of treatment and gender on students' performance in mathematics

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Remark
Corrected Model	21814.120 ^a	4	5453.530	35.820	.000	
Intercept	38963.503	1	38963.503	255.923	.000	
Pretest	236.987	1	236.987	1.557	.215	
Treatment	21254.213	1	21254.213	139.604	.000	Significant
Gender	21.038	1	21.038	.138	.711	Not Significant
Treatment* Gender	18.941	1	18.941	.124	.725	Not Significant
Error	18117.364	119	152.247			
Total	290312.000	124				
Corrected Total	39931.484	123				

a. R Squared = .546 (Adjusted R Squared = .531)

In table 1 above, there is significant main effect of treatment on students' performance in mathematics ($F(1,124) = 139.604$; $p = 0.000 < 0.05$). The treatment was found to be effective because the obtained p-value (0.000) is less than the alpha value of 0.05 for which the null hypothesis was tested. This implies that the posttest mean score of students exposed to writing-to-learn strategy differs significantly from the posttest mean score of students exposed to conventional method. The treatment was effective in enhancing students' performance in mathematics. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected.

H₀₂: There is no significant main effect of gender on students' performance in mathematics.

In table 1 above, there is no significant effect of gender on students' performance in mathematics. In other words, gender alone does not affect students' performance in mathematics ($F(1,124) = 0.138$; $p = 0.711 > 0.05$). This means that male and female students do not differ in their performance in mathematics. Therefore, the null hypothesis is upheld.

H₀₃: There is no significant interaction effect of treatment (writing-to-learn instructional strategy) and gender on students' performance in mathematics.

The results in table 1 shows that there is no interaction effect of treatment and gender on students' performance in mathematics ($F(1,124) = 0.124$; $p = 0.725 > 0.05$). This implies that when the treatment (writing-to-learn instructional strategy) is used in mathematics class, both male and female students will benefit equally. In other words, the treatment is not sensitive to the students' gender. Therefore, the null hypothesis is upheld.

Table 2: Main and Interaction effects of treatment and gender on students' retention of mathematics knowledge/concepts

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Remark
Corrected Model	15646.143 ^a	4	3911.536	34.618	.000	
Intercept	29433.665	1	29433.665	260.495	.000	
Pretest	765.425	1	765.425	6.774	.010	
Treatment	14267.230	1	14267.230	126.269	.000	Significant
Gender	20.413	1	20.413	.181	.672	Not Significant
Treatment * Gender	19.796	1	19.796	.175	.676	Not Significant
Error	13445.946	119	112.991			
Total	244231.000	124				
Corrected Total	29092.089	123				

a. R Squared = .538 (Adjusted R Squared = .522)

H₀4: There is no significant main effect of treatment (writing-to-learn strategy) on students' retention in mathematics.

In table 2 above, there is a significant effect of treatment on students' retention in mathematics ($F(1,124) = 126.269$; $p = 0.000 < 0.05$). The treatment was found to be effective because the obtained p value of 0.00 is less than the alpha value of 0.05 for which the null hypothesis was tested. The treatment was effective in enhancing students' retention in mathematics. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected.

H₀5: There is no significant main effect of gender on students' retention in mathematics.

The result of table 2 above shows that there is no significant effect of gender on students' retention in mathematics ($F(1,124) = 0.181$; $p = 0.672 > 0.05$). In other words, gender alone does not affect students' retention ability. This means that male and female students do not differ in their retention of mathematics knowledge after being exposed to treatment. The null hypothesis is therefore upheld. Table 2 equally shows that there is no significant interaction effect of gender and treatment on students' retention in Mathematics ($F(1,124) = 0.175$; $P = 0.672 > 0.05$).

Table 3: Comparison of experimental and Control Groups at Pretest, Posttest and Retention Test Stages

	Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	df	T	P	Remark
Pretest	Experimental	62	18.61	8.81	1.12	122	0.041	0.967	NS
	Control	62	18.55	8.70	1.10				
Posttest	Experimental	62	58.11	12.26	1.56	122	11.949	0.000	S
	Control	62	31.76	12.30	1.56				
Retention	Experimental	62	52.60	10.98	1.39	122	11.279	0.000	S
	Control	62	30.71	10.62	1.35				

NS=Not Significant ($p>0.05$)

S= Significant ($p<0.05$)

Table 3 shows that there is no significant difference between the pretest mean scores of experimental and control groups before the treatment (writing-to-learning instructional strategy) was used ($t=0.04$; $p = 0.967 > 0.05$). The experimental and control groups were at the same level of performance in mathematics before treatment was used. The mean for experimental group is 18.61 while that of control group is 18.55. This finding confirms that no group of students has initial advantage over the other. This also allows any difference in mean scores observed at the post-test stage to be attributed to the effect of treatment only.

Table 3 also shows that there is a significant difference between the posttest mean scores of experimental and control groups ($t=11.949$, $p = 0.000 < 0.05$). The experimental group has a significantly higher mean score (Mean=58.11) than the control group (Mean=31.76) this shows that the treatment has significant effect on students' performance in mathematics.

Again, table 3 equally shows that there is a significant difference between the retention mean scores of experimental and control groups ($t=11.279$, $p = 0.000 < 0.05$). The experimental group has a significantly higher mean (Mean=52.60) than the control group (Mean=30.71). This shows that the treatment has significant effect on students' retention of mathematics knowledge/concepts.

DISCUSSION

This study hypothesized that there is no significant main effect of treatment (WTL) on the senior secondary school students' performance in Mathematics. However, the result revealed that there is a significant main effect of treatment (WTL) on senior secondary school students' performance in Mathematics, in favour of the experimental group. The finding suggests that Writing to Learn (WTL) strategy significantly improved students' learning of Mathematics compared to the conventional method of teaching. This result is in support of the previous outcome of the effectiveness of WTL strategy for learning Mathematics (Joedeve, & Maere, 2023; Umoren, et al 2024). However, the finding contradicts the submission of Pantimo et al. (2015) which states that Writing to Learn strategy has no significant effect on students' achievement in Mathematics.

The study equally focused on determining the effect of gender on students' performance in Mathematics when taught using WTL strategy. The result of the study indicated that gender is not a significant factor affecting students' performance in Mathematics. This is in line with the finding of Umoren et al. (2024) that there is no significant difference between the mean

achievement scores of male and female students taught using writing to learn teaching approach.

On the interaction effect of gender and treatment on students' achievement in mathematics, the outcome of the study revealed that there is no significant interaction effect of gender and teaching strategy (WTL) on students' performance in Mathematics. This implies that both male and female benefited equally in mathematics learning from the teaching strategy. This finding is congruent to the discovery of Umoren et al. (2024) that the main effect of gender and interaction effect with the teaching strategy (WTL) were not significant on the performance of students in Mathematics. Additionally, the result of this study also showed that there is a significant main effect of strategy (WTL) on students' retention in Mathematics. This finding corroborated with the submission of Terada (2021) that writing about content material facilitates learning by consolidating information in a long term memory. It is also in tandem with the finding of Keyaalp (2022) on retention that the experimental group exposed to writing to learn teaching strategy showed knowledge retention over time in writing skills than their counterpart in the control group.

It was equally discovered from the study that there is no significant main effect of gender on retention in Mathematics when taught using writing to learn and also no interaction effect of gender and strategy (WTL) on students' retention in Mathematics. This simply means that WTL teaching strategy is not sensitive to gender.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study investigated the effect of writing-to-learn (WTL) instructional strategy on senior secondary school students' performance in Mathematics. From the result of the study, it was discovered that there was a significant effect of the strategy (WTL) on students' performance in Mathematics, there was no significant effect of gender on student performance in mathematics when taught using WTL strategy, the strategy (WTL) is not sensitive to gender, it equally improved students' retention of mathematics knowledge and there was no interaction effect of gender and strategy (WTL) on students' retention of mathematics knowledge. Before the discovery of the effectiveness of active learning teaching strategy such as writing-to-learn, mathematics teachers have been using conventional method of teaching to teach mathematics, and it was having positive effect on students' performance but not as much as active learning strategy (WTL). Therefore, conventional method should not be totally condemned, rather, it should be used in combination with other active learning strategy such as WTL for better performance of students in Mathematics.

Consequently, it is recommended that mathematics teacher should intensively adopt the use of WTL strategy in the teaching and learning of Mathematics since it has a tremendous effect on students' performance. It is also recommended that teacher education programme meant to produce mathematics teachers in the senior secondary schools should include the strategy (WTL) as one of the mathematics method in the programme. Again, seminars and workshops should be organized by the government and school heads for mathematics teachers to gain the rubrics of writing-to-learn teaching strategy.

It is equally recommended that the efficacy of this strategy (WTL) be tested in other levels (primary, junior secondary, tertiary) of education.

References

- Abiodun, T.O., Asanre, A.A., Ogundeji, M.A. Odupe, T.A. & Rasaki, M.G. (2022), Effect of Think-Pair-Share Strategy on Students' Achievement in Senior Secondary School Mathematics, *Journal of Mathematics and Science Education*, 3(2), 20-25.
- Adeniyi, C. O. (2012), Effect of Personalized System of Instruction on Senior School Students' Performance in Mathematics in Kwara South, Nigeria. Unpublished Ph.D Thesis, University of Ilorin, Ilorin Nigeria.
- Aduwa, J. (2021), The Essential Qualities of An Effective Mathematics Teacher In Teaching Profession: Secondary Schools In Nigeria In Focus. *International Journal of Education and Evaluation*, 7(1), 48 – 54.
- Achuonye, K. A. (2015), Predominant Teaching Strategies in Schools: Implications for Curriculum Implementation in Mathematics, Science and Technology. *Academic Journals* 10(5), 2096-2103.
- Ajai, J.T.&Imoko. B.I.(2015), Gender Difference In Mathematics Achievement and Retention Scores; A Case Of Problem Based Learning Method, *International Journal of Research In Education and Science (IJRES)*, 1(1), 45-50.
- Akanm, M. A. (2013), Effects of Guided Discovery Learning and Cognitive Styles on Senior School Students' Performance in Mathematics in Ejigbo Nigeria. Unpublished Ph.D Thesis.University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Nigeria.
- Akinoso, S.O. (2015), Teaching Mathematics in A Volatile, Unknown, Complex and Ambiguous (VUCA) World: The Use of Concrete Representational-Abstract-Instructional Strategy. *Journal of The International Society For Teacher Education*, 19, 92 – 107.
- Anari, M.I., Nja, C.O. & Neji, H.A. (2023), Interaction effect of Gender and Instructional Strategies on Academic Achievement and Retention in Chemistry. *Inter-Disciplinary Journal of Science Education (IJSED)*, 4(2), 129 – 136.
- Anokye-Poku, D. & Ampadu, E. (2020), Gender Difference in Attitudes and Achievement in Mathematics Among Ghanaian Junior High School Students. *International Journal of Education*, 12(3), 84 – 95.
- Aransi,W.O. (2018), The Influence of School Type, Class Classification and Gender On Academic Achievement In Economics Among High School Students: A Comparative Analysis. *International Journal of Progressive Science and Technology*, 8(2), 120 – 128.
- Arend, R. (1998), Resource Handbook, Learning to Teach, (4thed), pp 12, Boston, MA McGraw-Hill.
- Bature, I.J., Atewe, B. & Treagust, D. (2026), Inclusivity: An Effective Tool for Achieving Quality Mathematics Classroom Instruction in Nigerian Secondary Schools. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 4(1), 123 – 180.

- Chmarkh, M. (2020), Writing-to-Learn Research: A Synthesis of Empirical Studies (2004-2019). *European Journal of Educational Research*, 10(1), 85-96.
- Deveci, T. (2018), Writing For and Because Of Lifelong Learning. *European Journal of Educational Research*, 8(1), 1 – 7.
- Elliot, S.N. (2000). *Educational Psychology; Effective Teaching, Effective Learning*. (3rded) pp 7. Boston MA McGraw-Hill College.
- Enikanolaye, A. J., Salman, M.F., Akanmu, M.A. & Salami O.O. (2018), Trend of Performance in Nigerian Unified Tertiary Matriculation Examination in Mathematics from 2012-2016. *ABACUS: The Journal of Mathematics Association of Nigeria*, 42(2), 161-166.
- Enikanolaye, A.J. (2021), Effect of Multimedia Instructional Strategy on Senior School Students' Performance and Retention in Mathematics. *Anatolian Journal of Education*, 6(2), 193-206.
- Fehintola, T.T. & Yahya, D.O. (2019), Effect of Gender on Economics Students' Academic Performance in Secondary Schools in Oyo, Nigeria. *British Journal of Education, Learning and Developmental Psychology*, 2(2), 102 – 106.
- Filgona, J. & Sababa, I.K. (2017), Effects of Gender On Senior Secondary School Students' Achievement In Geography In Ganye Educational Zone, Nigeria. *European Journal of Educational Studies*, 3(4), 349 – 410.
- Forgasz, H.J. Leder, G.C. & Vale, C. (2017), Gender and Mathematics: Changing Perspective. *Journal of Education and Technology*, 18(1), 161-168.
- Fry, S. & Villagomez, A. (2012), Writing-to-Learn: Benefits and Limitations. *Coll Teach*, 60, 170-175.
- Gogo, Z.I. & Nduka, W. (2017). Comprehensive Analysis of Students' Mathematics Achievement In West African Senior Secondary Certificate Examination In Nigeria. *European Journal Of Research and Reflection In Educational Science*. 5(1), 24 – 31
- Guwam, B. & Gwandum, G.S. (2017), Effect of Elaboration Strategy on Students' Performance and Anxiety In Bearing and Distance At Secondary School Two (2) Level In Plateau State, Nigeria. *Journal of Mathematics Association of Nigeria: Abacus*, 42(2), 8 – 15.
- Iji, C.O. & Uka, N.K. (2012), Influence of Teachers' Qualification on Students' Mathematics Achievement and Interest in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State. *ABACUS: Journal of Mathematics Association of Nigeria*, 37(1), 38 – 48.
- Incirci, A. & Parmaksiz, R.S. (2016), The Effect of Writing-to-Learn (WTL) on Academic Achievement and Attitude To Lesson in English Class, *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 4(9), 2163-2173. Retrieved 20th May 2023 From <https://www.hrpub.org>

- International Mathematics Union, (2019), *Mathematics Is Everywhere: Proclamation by UNESCO of March 14 As International Day For Mathematics*, Retrieved 10th March, 2024 From <https://www.mathunion.org/fileadmin/IMU/PressRelease/2019-11-24/Press-Release-IDM-en-v2.pdf>
- Jacob, F. & Linus, K.S. (2017), Effects of Gender on Secondary School Students' Academic Achievement in Geography in Ganye Educational Zone, Nigeria. *European Journal of Educational Studies*, 3(4), 394-410.
- Kayaalp, F., Meral, E. & Namli, Z.B. (2022), An Analysis Of The Effect Of Writing-to-Learn Activities Regarding Students' Academic Achievement and Self Regulation Skills In Writing, *Participatory Educational Research (PER)* 9(1), 324-348. Retrieved 2nd March 2022, From <https://www.perjournal.com>
- Kaur, T. & Prendergast, M. (2021), Students' Perceptions of Mathematics Writing and Its Impact on Their Enjoyment and Self Confidence. *Teaching Mathematics and Its Applications: An International Journal of IMA*, 00, 1 – 21, doi:10.1093/teamat/hrab008.
- Kumar, M.S. & Wonu, S. (2022), Factors Affecting The Mathematics Learning Outcome of Under Achieving Students at College of Education. *Journal of Mathematics and Science Education*, 3(2), 1 – 10.
- McLeod, S.A. (2019). Constructivism As A Theory For Teaching and Learning. Retrieved 10th November 2021, From <https://www.simplepsychology.org/constructivism.html>.
- Mohammed. A. (3010), *Factors That Influence Secondary School Students' Performance in Mathematics in Banadir Region, Somalia*. Unpublished Thesis Submitted to The Department Education, Kenyatta University, Kenya
- Muema, J., Mulwa, D. & Mailu, S., (2018), Relationship Between Teaching Method and Students' Performance In Mathematics In Public Secondary Schools In dadaab sub County, Garissa County, Kenya, *Journal of Research and Method of Education*, 8(5),59 – 63.
- Nugroho, K.Y. & Wulandari, D.F. (2017), Constructivist Learning Paradigm As The Basis On Learning Model Development. *Journal of Education and Learning*, 409(4), 410 – 415.
- Nyakomba, K.Z. (2017), *Relationship Between Students' Mathematics Achievement and Career in Secondary Schools in Kandara Sub-Country, Kenya*. A Master Degree Thesis Submitted to Kenyatta University, Kenya, Retrieved 25 July 2024 from <https://tr.library.ku.ac.ke/bit-stream/handle/123456789/18158>.
- Obidile, H.I. & Uzoekwe, H.E. (2018), Influence of Gender on Accounting Students' Academic Achievement and Retention in Secondary Schools In Anambra State, Nigeria. *International Multidisciplinary Journal, AFRREV*, 12(4), 87 – 94.
- Ogbeba, J.A. (2010), Using Advance Organizers to Improve The Teaching and Learning of Biology: A Case for Specific Objectives. *Journal of Educational Innovations*, 2(2), 184 – 190.

- Oliver, K.M., (2000), Methods For Developing Constructivism Learning on The Web. *Journal of Educational Technology*, 40(6), 5 – 18.
- Oloda, F.S.S, Ojo, S.G. & Durojaiye, D.S. (2024), Methods and Strategies for Effective Teaching of Mathematics in Secondary Schools in Nigeria. *Teacher Education and Curriculum Studies*, 9(4), 103 – 109.
- Oribharbor, C.B. (2019), The Influence of Gender on Mathematics Achievement of Secondary School Students in Bayelsa State, Nigeria, *African Journal of Studies in Education* 14(2), 196-206).
- Pantino, F.O. Quimbo, M.T. & Pantino, J.H. (2015), Effect of Creative Writing on Students' Achievement in Mathematics, *West Visayas State University: WVSU Research Journal*, 4(1), 1-11. Retrieved 11TH November 2022, From <https://urdc.WVSU.ph/urdcjournals/wp-content/upload/2017/07/Eff...tive-Writing-Activities-on-Student-Achievement-in-Mathematics-1.pdf>
- Pugalee, D.K. (2014), Writing Mathematics and Metacognition: Looking For Connection Through Students' Work in Mathematics Problem Solving. *School, Science and Mathematics*, 101(5), 236 – 245.
- Seo, B. (2015), Mathematical Writing: What Is It and How Do We Teach It? *Journal of Humanistic Mathematics*, 5(2), 133-145. Retrieved 25th February, 2023, From <https://scholarship.claremont.edu/jhn/vol5/iss2/12>.
- Schanumburg, H. (2001), *Fostering Girls Computer Literacy Level out the Gender Difference?* Paper presented at the NECC Conference, Jun 25-27, Chicago, IL.
- Sunday, A.O. & Honmane, O. (2023) A Critical Review of Problems Facing Mathematics Teaching In Basic Schools In Nigeria. *Journal of Science, Research and Teaching*, 2(3), 15 – 21.
- Tam, M. (2000), Constructivism Instructional Design: Implication For Transforming Distance Learning. *Journal of Educational Technology and Society*, 3(2), 50 – 60.
- Terada, Y. (2021), Why Students Should Write In All Subjects, Retrieved 10th December, 2023, From <https://www.edutopia.org/article/why-students-should-write-in-all-subjects/>
- Teuscher, D., Hodges, K.P. & Crooker, C. (2015), Writing to Learn Mathematics: An updated. *The Mathematics Educator*, 24(2), 56-78.
- Ugwu, P.N. (2011), Reappraising The Current National Policy on Education for Functionality and Self Reliance: Issues and Challenges for Mathematics Education. *Journal of Qualitative Education*, 7(1),1 – 5.
- Umoren, U.J., Allahoki, N.D., Ezeh, S.I. & Inekwe, I.O. (2024), Writing to Learn, Gender and Effects on Mathematics Achievement of Senior Secondary School Students in Akwa Ibom state, Nigeria. *International Journal of Research*, 5(2), 466 – 470.

- Urguhart, V. (2009), Using writing in Mathematics to Deepen Students' Learning. Retrieved 22 July 2024, from www.mcrel.org.
- Utibe, U.J. & Agwagah, U.N. (2015). Decades of Candidates' Performances In NECO-SSCE Mathematics In Nigeria. *Journal Of Education and Practice*, 6(25), 25 – 29.
- Yara, P.O. & Otieno, K.O. (2010), Teaching/Learning Resources and Academic Performance in Secondary Schools in Bondo District of Kenya. *Journal of Asian Social Science*, 6(12), 115 – 125.
- Yusuk, S. (2020). Perception and Practices of EFL School Teachers on Implementing Active Learning In Thai English Language Classroom, *Thailand Tesol: ThAITESOL Journal*, 33(1), 36 – 55, Retrieved June 3rd, 2022 From <https://files.eric.edu.gov/fulltext/EJ1257621.pdf>